

SOFTLY NORMAL TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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RECEIVED : 30 January, 2015

REVISED : 19 April, 2015

In the present paper, we introduce a weaker version of normality called soft-normality. We will prove that soft-normality is a property, which is implied by quasi-normality and almost-normality. We prove that soft-normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspace.

2010 AMS Subject classification: 54D15

KEYWORDS AND PHRASES: regular closed, π -closed, π -open sets; quasi normal and softly normal spaces.

INTRODUCTION

In 1968, the notion of a quasi normality is a weaker form of normality was introduced by Zaitsev [11]. In 1970, the concept of almost normality was introduced by Singal and Arya [6]. In 1973, the notion of mild normality was introduced by Shchepin [8] and Singal and Singal [7] independently. In 1990, Lal and Rahman [4] have further studied notion of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. In 2008, π -normal topological spaces were introduced by Kalantan [2]. In 2011, Thabit and Kamarulhaili [9] presented some characterizations of weakly (resp. almost) regular spaces. Also object of this paper is to present some conditions to assure that the product of two spaces will be π -normal. In 2012, Thabit and Kamarulhaili [10] introduced a weaker version of p -normality called πp -normality and obtained some basic properties, examples, characterizations and preservation theorems of this property are presented. In 2014, Patil, Benchalli and Gonnagar [5] introduced and studied two new classes of spaces, namely $\omega\alpha$ -normal and $\omega\alpha$ -regular spaces and obtained their properties by utilizing $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets. In 2015, Hamant *et al.* [1] introduce a new class of normal spaces is called $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces, by using $\pi g\beta$ -open sets. We proved that $\pi g\beta$ -normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to π -open, $\pi g\beta$ -closed subspace. Further we obtain a characterization and preservation theorems for $\pi g\beta$ -normal spaces.

In the present paper, we introduce a weaker version of normality called soft-normality. We will prove that soft-normality is a property, which is implied by quasi-normality and

almost-normality. We prove that soft-normality is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspace.

PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, τ) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be regular open [3] (resp. regular closed [3]) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be π -open. The complement of a π -open set is said to be π -closed.

Remark. Every regular open (resp. regular closed) set is π -open (resp. π -closed).

SOFTLY-NORMAL SPACES

3.1. Definition. A space X is called π -normal [2] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.2. Definition. A space X is called almost normal [6] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is regular closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.3. Definition. A space X is called quasi normal [11] if for any two disjoint π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.4. Definition. A space X is called softly normal if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed and other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.5. Definition. A space X is called mildly normal [7, 8] if for any two disjoint regularly closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagrams [2]:

$$\text{normal} \Rightarrow \pi\text{-normal} \Rightarrow \text{almost normal} \Rightarrow \text{softly normal} \Rightarrow \text{mildly normal}$$

and

$$\text{normal} \Rightarrow \pi\text{-normal} \Rightarrow \text{quasi normal} \Rightarrow \text{softly normal} \Rightarrow \text{mildly normal}.$$

3.6. Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (i) X is softly-normal.
- (ii) For every π -closed set A and every regularly open set B with $A \subset B$, there exists an open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset B$.
- (iii) For every regularly closed set A and every π -open set B with $A \subset B$, there exists an open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset B$.
- (iv) For every pair consisting of disjoint sets A and B , one of which is π -closed and the other is regularly closed, there exist open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof.

(i) \Rightarrow (ii). Assume (i). Let A be any π -closed set and B be any regularly open set such that $A \subset B$. Then $A \cap (X - B) = \emptyset$, where $(X - B)$ is regularly closed. Then there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $(X - B) \subset V$. Since $U \cap V = \emptyset$, then $\text{cl}(U) \cap V = \emptyset$. Thus $\text{cl}(U) \subset (X - V) \subseteq (X - (X - B)) = B$. Therefore, $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset B$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Assume (ii). Let A be any regularly closed set and B be any π -open set such that $A \subset B$. Then, $(X - B) \subset (X - A)$, where $(X - B)$ is π -closed and $(X - A)$ is regularly open. Thus by (ii), there exists an open set W such that $(X - B) \subset W \subset \text{cl}(W) \subset (X - A)$. Thus $A \subset (X - \text{cl}(W)) \subset (X - W) \subset B$. So, let $U = (X - \text{cl}(W))$, which is open and since $W \subset \text{cl}(W)$, then $(X - \text{cl}(W)) \subset (X - W)$. Thus $U \subset (X - W)$, hence $\text{cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(X - W) = (X - W) \subset B$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Assume (iii). Let A be any regular closed set and B be any π -closed set with $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Then $A \subset (X - B)$, where $(X - B)$ is π -open. By (iii), there exists an open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset (X - B)$. Now, $\text{cl}(U)$ is closed. Applying (iii) again we get an open set W such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset W \subset \text{cl}(W) \subset (X - B)$. Let $V = (X - \text{cl}(W))$, then V is open set and $B \subset V$. We have $(X - \text{cl}(W)) \subset (X - W)$, hence $V \subset (X - W)$, thus $\text{cl}(V) \subset \text{cl}(X - W) = (X - W)$. So, we have $\text{cl}(U) \subset W$ and $\text{cl}(V) \subset (X - W)$. Therefore $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i) is clear.

Using Theorem 3.6, it is easy to show the following theorem, which is a Urysohn's Lemma version for soft normality. A proof can be established by a similar way of the normal case.

3.7. Theorem. A space X is softly-normal if and only if for every pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , one of which is π -closed and other is regularly closed, there exists a continuous function f on X into $[0, 1]$, with its usual topology, such that $f(A) = \{0\}$ and $f(B) = \{1\}$.

It is easy to see that the inverse image of a regularly closed set under an open continuous function is regularly closed and the inverse image of a π -closed set under an open continuous function π -closed. We will use that in the next theorem.

3.8. Theorem. Let X is a softly normal space and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an open continuous injective function. Then $f(X)$ is a softly normal space.

Proof. Let A be any π -closed subset in $f(X)$ and let B be any regularly closed subset in $f(X)$ such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Then $f^{-1}(A)$ is a π -closed set in X , which is disjoint from the regularly closed set $f^{-1}(B)$. Since X is softly normal, there are two disjoint open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$. Since f is 1-1 and open, result follows.

3.9. Corollary. Soft normality is a topological property.

3.10. Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If A is an open set in X , then $A \cap M$ is open set in M .

3.11. Theorem. A closed domain subspace of a softly normal space is softly normal.

Proof. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a softly normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint closed sets in M such that A is regularly closed and B is π -closed. Then, A and B are disjoint closed sets in X such that A is regularly closed and B is π -closed in X . By soft normality of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. By the Lemma 3.10, we have $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint open sets in M such that $A \subset U \cap M$ and $B \subset V \cap M$. Hence, M is softly normal subspace.

Since every closed and open (clopen) subset is a closed domain, then we have the following corollary.

3.12. Corollary. Soft normality is a hereditary with respect to clopen subspaces.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced weak form of normality namely softly-normality and established their relationships with some weak forms of normal spaces in topological spaces.

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